

The sharp clock.

This is a other one time geometrical clock:

Note: with mono-crystal space and mono-prism time, this is again a other one time prism (crystal space), that uses Euclidean geometry, therefore the other one time based parts to this geometrical prism clock are similar to a space crystal clock, however not the same, because a mono-time model has no concept of a spatial model, and a mono-spatial model has no concept of a temporal model, there are just again similarities. Here is an example of what a other one time sphere looks like:

So therefore similar to a cube, however not quite the same.